

Unsteady Transient Free Convective Flow of an Incompressible Viscous Fluid under Influence of Uniform Transverse Magnetic Field

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Abstract : The unsteady transient free convection flow of an incompressible dissipative viscous fluid in between parallel plates at a distanced three is porous medium. Due to presence of heat flux under the influence of uniform transverse magnetic field. The velocity distribution the temperature distribution, coefficient of skin friction & rate of heat transfer has been investigated. Since exact solution is not possible, we find parametrical solution by perturbation technique. The result is shown in graph for different parameter. We notice that heat generation effects fluid velocity keeping in which of free convection which cools.

Keywords : Transient, Convection, MHD, Incompressible, Viscous, Porous

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